

**Synthesis, Modelling, and Catalytic Properties of HY Zeolite-Supported Rhodium
Dinitrosyl Complexes**

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ABSTRACT:

HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes were used as precursors for the surface mediated synthesis of Rh(NO)₂ species. The results of FTIR, EXAFS, and Mass Spectrometry measurements, as well as DFT calculations show that the replacement of the CO ligands in the Rh(CO)₂ complexes by NO is a facile substitution process which is not affected by the Si/Al ratio of the zeolite support used. The Rh(NO)₂ complexes thus formed are site-isolated 14-electron species with a Rh–N bond distance of 1.77 Å, a N–Rh–N angle of ~104°, and NO ligands significantly deviating from a linear configuration (Rh–N–O angle ~148°). These species exhibit a characteristic set of well-defined ν_{NO} bands at 1855 and 1779 cm⁻¹ in their FTIR spectra and have an additional empty d-orbital at the rhodium center allowing for coordination of a third electron-donating ligand. Therefore, the Rh(NO)₂ species react with C₂H₄ to form 16-electron Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄) species which are stable in the presence of gas phase C₂H₄ and can be further converted into Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₅) complexes by addition of H₂. The Rh(NO)₂/HY30 material catalyzed both C₂H₄ hydrogenation and dimerization reactions at room temperature with TOFs of 0.01 and 6.7 · 10⁻³ s⁻¹ at steady state, respectively. During these processes, the Rh sites remain mono-dispersed. An inverse kinetic isotope effect was observed for both reactions, thus underlining the similarities of the catalytic properties of the supported Rh(NO)₂ species examined and molecular organometallic Rh complexes in solution. This is the first example demonstrating that Rh dinitrosyl complexes anchored on a solid support can catalyze hydrocarbon reactions.

Keywords: Rhodium nitrosyl complexes; Supported rhodium complexes; HY zeolite; DFT calculations; Ethene hydrogenation; Ethene dimerization; in situ FTIR; HRSTEM catalyst imaging.

1. INTRODUCTION

Molecular organometallic complexes of rhodium are widely used as catalysts in a variety of important homogeneous catalytic reactions such as carbonylation of methanol and methyl acetate to acetic acid and acetic anhydride, respectively, hydroformylation of alkenes to aldehydes, and hydrogenation of alkenes and aldehydes to the corresponding alkanes and alcohols.^{1,2} More recent reports indicate that molecular organometallic complexes of rhodium can also be used for the processing of biomass or biomass derived platform chemicals with high selectivities. For example, hydroformylation of fatty acids catalyzed by Rh complexes yields formyl-functionalized fatty acids, which can be further hydrogenated to form hydroxylated fatty acids currently used for material synthesis.³ It has been also reported that $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ and $[\text{RhCl}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14})_2]_2$ complexes are efficient catalysts for the selective isomerization of the double bonds in fatty acids to form conjugated derivatives that can be used as food additives or starting materials for the production of polymers, coatings, and paints.³ While the Rh complexes typically used in these applications are relatively active and offer high selectivity levels, challenges are also present related to their fast deactivation and separation from reaction products.⁴ Supported catalytic materials can be easily separated from the products in slurry reactions or can be used in fix-bed configurations. Therefore, the development of mononuclear single-site heterogeneous catalysts, which can retain their structural integrity and catalytic properties under reaction conditions, is very attractive.⁵

Substantial research efforts have been focused on the synthesis of heterogeneous analogs of molecular complexes, their chemical reactivity, and catalytic applications. Often, supported metal complexes were found to be site-isolated and molecular in nature with reactivity patterns resembling those of corresponding molecular analogs in solution.⁶⁻¹¹ Such model catalysts have been used to develop a better understanding of elemental steps of catalytic reactions. There are literature reports, however, demonstrating some unexpected catalytic properties of such materials. For example, it has been shown that HY-zeolite supported $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ and $\text{Ir}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ complexes exhibit not only hydrogenation but also ethene dimerization activity to form n-butenes.^{12,13} The ability of these halide-free single-site Rh and Ir complexes to convert ethene in the presence of H_2 into long-chain hydrocarbons appears to be quite unique, since $[\text{Rh}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{Cl}]_2$ is the only known molecular Rh complex capable of catalyzing such a reaction in the liquid-phase.¹⁴ On the other hand, it remains largely unknown how both hydrogenation and dimerization reactions occur simultaneously over the same metal sites in these materials,

although a bifunctional mechanism for C₂H₄ dimerization that includes the participation of support sites has been proposed.¹⁵

Our own data show that both ethene hydrogenation and dimerization reactions also occur over HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ and Rh(CO)(C₂H₄) complexes and the reactivity patterns observed over these two samples are similar.¹⁶ In this case, both the high reactivity of CO ligands and the almost instantaneous conversion of Rh(CO)₂ into Rh(CO)(C₂H₄) complexes in the presence of gas-phase C₂H₄ appear to eliminate any potential effects of different ligands that are initially present on the Rh sites.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ As a result, both complexes produce the same type of intermediates under reaction conditions and, therefore, exhibit similar catalytic properties.

Therefore, the presence alone of CO and C₂H₄ ligands on supported Rh sites does not significantly alter C₂H₄ hydrogenation and dimerization reactivity patterns and cannot lead to a better understanding of the elementary steps involved in these reactions. Thus, it appears that supported metal complexes with ligands of more diverse nature are required to probe the effects of ligands on the electronic and catalytic properties in single-site supported metal catalysts. Along these lines, the use of organometallic complexes incorporating nitrosyl ligands provides a promising alternative. Preparation procedures and structural parameters have been reported for a large number of organometallic Rh complexes with such nitrosyl ligands.²⁰⁻²³ However, only limited examples can be found in literature where the catalytic properties of such complexes have been examined in detail. In one such example, Rh(NO)(PPh₃)₃ and Rh(NO)(PPh₃)₂L (L= p-benzoquinone) complexes were found to be active for liquid-phase hydrogenation of various alkenes.²⁴⁻²⁶ The elementary steps of the hydrogenation reactions taking place over these complexes remain largely unknown, although the formation of Rh(NO)(PPh₃)₂(alkene) species in the presence of excess alkene has been suggested. Another example includes CO₂ hydrogenation to formic acid over Rh(NO)(dcpe) (dcpe = 1,2-dicyclohexylphosphinoethane) complexes that likely involves Rh(NO)-hydride intermediates.²⁷ Finally, it has been reported that the Rh(NO)(PPh₃)₃ complex reacts with HCl to give Rh(NO)(OH)Cl₃(PPh₃)₂ and Rh(HNO)Cl₃(PPh₃)₂ tautomers.²⁴ This result suggests that the mechanisms of the reactions occurring over such complexes could also incorporate oxidative addition steps.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no reports describing the synthesis of heterogeneous analogs for molecular rhodium nitrosyl complexes, although the adsorption of NO on extended Rh surfaces and supported Rh particles is well documented.²⁸⁻³² In the latter case, for example, it has been shown that the exposure of γ -Al₂O₃-supported Rh particles with sizes on the order of 10 nm to NO at temperatures below 200°C leads to their disruption into monodispersed

Rh(NO)₂ species.^{30,31} While the Rh(NO)₂ complexes thus prepared constitute the majority of the surface species following the exposure to NO, some small Rh particles or clusters could also remain on the non-uniform support surface.

A surface-mediated chemistry approach allows for the preparation of materials that are more structurally uniform. For example, it has been shown that solid-state ion exchange can be used to introduce Rh³⁺ cations to a H-ZSM-5 framework and subsequently form Rh⁺(CO)₂ and Rh²⁺(CO)₂ complexes upon exposure to CO.³³ Rh²⁺(CO)₂(NO) and/or Rh⁺(NO)₂ complexes can be formed from such rhodium dicarbonyl species, although it remains unclear how well these complexes are distributed over the ZSM-5 framework, since no direct structural data have been provided for these materials.

It has been further shown that various Rh acetylacetonate complexes can readily react with the surface of dealuminated HY zeolites to yield well-defined Rh species anchored to the zeolite framework.^{12,17-19,34,35} In these reports, the single-site nature of such complexes was established by EXAFS measurements and was confirmed by DFT calculations. These Rh complexes chemically bound to zeolite frameworks represent the best-known examples of uniform solid catalytic materials with site-isolated single metal sites. Furthermore, we have also shown that these HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ species can be used to selectively form Rh(CO)(C₂H₄) or Rh(CO)(H)_x complexes upon subsequent exposure to C₂H₄ and H₂ at room temperature.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

Since literature examples also indicate that NO can replace the CO ligands of supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes,^{17,36,37} the goal of this research is to prepare Rh(NO)₂ complexes from HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ species and to examine in detail their structural, chemical, and catalytic properties. FTIR, MS, XAS, HRSTEM measurements, as well as DFT calculations were used to clarify the structure and nature of the Rh(NO)₂ surface species formed. The results obtained indicate that Rh(NO)₂ complexes thus formed are site-isolated, molecular in nature, and the chemical properties of the nitrosyl ligands are significantly different from those of carbonyls due to different type of bonding of the ligands to the rhodium center. Nevertheless, the HY zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes formed were found to be active for C₂H₄ hydrogenation and oligomerization reactions. In fact, the results of the kinetic measurements reported herein represent the first known experimental evidence of alkene hydrogenation catalyzed by supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes. Furthermore, the successful synthesis of HY zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ species expands the family of known single-site supported Rh complexes with well-defined structures and ligand environments and provides an opportunity to determine at the molecular level how nature and electronic properties of various ligands affect the catalytic properties of single Rh sites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Reagents and Materials. Dicarbonyl(acetylacetonato) rhodium (I) $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$ ($\text{acac} = \text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$) (Strem, 98% purity) was used as supplied. *n*-Pentane (Aldrich, 99% purity) was refluxed under N_2 in the presence of Na/benzophenone ketyl to remove traces of moisture and deoxygenated by sparging of dry N_2 prior to use. All glassware used in preparation steps was previously dried at 120°C . H_2 , He, NO, and C_2H_4 (Airgas, all UHP grade) were additionally purified prior to their use by passage through oxygen/moisture traps (Agilent) capable of removing traces of O_2 and water to 15 and 25 ppb, respectively. CBV760, CBV720, and CBV600 dealuminated HY zeolites (Zeolyst International) with Si/Al atomic ratios of 30, 15, and 2.6, respectively, were calcined in O_2 at 400°C for 5 h, evacuated at 10^{-3} Torr and 400°C for 16 h, and stored in a glovebox (MBraun) filled with N_2 prior to use. The residual water and O_2 concentrations in the glovebox were kept below 0.1 ppm. For simplicity, these supports are further denoted as HY30, HY15, and HY2.6, respectively.

2.2. Preparation of supported samples. All syntheses and sample transfer procedures were performed with exclusion of air and moisture on a double-manifold Schlenk line and in a N_2 -filled MBraun glovebox. Zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes were prepared by slurring the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$ precursor with the corresponding powder support in *n*-pentane under N_2 for 24 h at room temperature, followed by overnight evacuation at 25°C to remove the solvent. In each case, the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$ precursor was added in the amount needed to yield samples containing 1 wt.% Rh. The Rh weight loading was verified by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis (Galbraith Laboratories Inc.). The prepared samples were stored and handled in a glovebox filled with N_2 to prevent possible decomposition of the supported species. $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}$ samples were prepared by exposure of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY}$ to a 1% NO/He mixture for 1 h with a subsequent treatment in He for 5 h at 25°C .

2.3. FTIR spectroscopy. A Nicolet Nexus 470 spectrometer equipped with a MCT-B detector cooled by liquid nitrogen was used to collect spectra with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} , averaging 64 scans per spectrum. Each powder sample was pressed into a self-supported wafer with a density of approximately 20 mg/cm^2 and mounted in a home-made cell connected to a gas distribution manifold. The cell design allowed for the treatment of samples at different temperatures, while various gases were flowing through the cell.

2.4. Mass spectrometry measurements. Mass spectrometry (MS) measurements were used to monitor ligand exchange reactions between surface species and different gases and to identify the products released during such reactions. In a typical experiment, approximately 100 mg of the sample was loaded into a plug-flow micro reactor in a glovebox and the reactor was sealed to avoid air exposure. The reactor was subsequently connected to a gas distribution system equipped with mass flow controllers and an online Inficon Transpector 2 residual gas analyzer operating in a multi-ion detection mode. Before each experiment, the reactor was purged with He (100 ml/min) at 25°C and atmospheric pressure for 1 h to stabilize the baseline mass spectrometer signal. When this procedure was completed, various feeds (as specified in the text) were introduced into the reactor at 25°C and a flow rate of 100 ml/min. The feed and effluent compositions were routinely monitored with time on stream to detect species such as CO ($m/z=28$) and NO ($m/z=30$).

2.5. Computational details and models. Periodic DFT calculations were performed with the PW91 exchange-correlation functional³⁸ using a Vienna *ab initio* simulation package (VASP).^{39,40} Ultrasoft pseudopotentials^{41,42} were used as implemented in the VASP package. Due to the large size of the unit cell (see below), the Brillouin zone was sampled using only the Γ point.⁴³ SCF energy convergence of 10^{-4} eV is used. The N-O vibrational frequencies obtained with test calculations with a tighter SCF convergence criterion of 10^{-6} eV for the dinitrosyl complexes differ by up to 3 cm^{-1} from those obtained with 10^{-4} eV criterion. The valence wave functions were expanded in a plane-wave basis with a cutoff energy of 400 eV. Test calculations with higher cutoff energies (450 and 500 eV) showed that the binding energy (per ligand) of the NO ligands in the Rh(NO)₂ complex collaborates within 7 kJ/mol, while the N-O vibrational frequencies change by up to 3 cm^{-1} .

We also explored the influence of the dispersion interaction and the most important structures were also optimized with PW91+D2. The results are shown in Table S1 in SI. Dispersion correction does not change notably binding energies of NO ligands (it increases by 2 to 5 kJ/mol per ligand) and the simulated N-O vibrational frequencies are shifted by only 1-4 cm^{-1} , as only for the complex with two C₂H₄ molecules the shift is 10 cm^{-1} . Thus, the comparisons with experimental data and all conclusions based on the calculations without dispersion corrections are confirmed by the calculations with the PW91-D approach. Notable effect of the dispersion correction is found only on the absolute values of the adsorption energies of the hydrocarbon species adsorbed to the Rh(NO)₂ complex (discussed below) but the order of stability of different species is not altered.

In order to check if the calculated vibrational N-O frequencies will be affected if one uses a more rigorous computational approach we modeled three of the systems, Rh(NO)₂_a, Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄)_a, and Rh(NO)₂(H)(C₂H₄)_a, combining tighter convergence criteria of 0.02 eV/Å for geometry relaxation, 10⁻⁶ eV for the SCF convergence and cutoff energy of 500 eV, with PW91-D2 approach accounting for the dispersion interactions. The N-O frequencies change by only 1-5 cm⁻¹.

The cubic unit cell of the zeolite framework was optimized for the pure silicate structure with dimensions $a = b = c = 24.345 \text{ \AA}$.⁴⁴ To simulate the structure of a highly dealuminated HY zeolite, one Si atom in the unit cell was replaced with Al. The negative charge around the Al site was compensated by the Rh⁺ ion or its complexes. During the geometry optimization procedure, all the zeolite atoms and the adsorbate species were allowed to relax until the force on each atom was less than $5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ eV/\AA}$. Test calculations with convergence criteria of $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ eV/\AA}$ changed the total energy of the complexes by at most 4 kJ/mol and the N-O vibrational frequencies not more than 2 cm⁻¹.

The binding energy (BE) of the NO and other adsorbates (when applicable) was determined as: $\text{BE}[\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{X})^+/\text{Zeo}] = E[\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{X})^+/\text{Zeo}] - E[\text{Rh}^+/\text{Zeo}] - E[\text{NO}] - E[\text{X}]$, where $E[\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{X})^+/\text{Zeo}]$ is the energy of the zeolite system together with the metal cation and adsorbed NO and X (where X represents various different ligands such as NO, H₂ or 1/2H₂, C₂H₄, C₂H₅, trans-C₄H₈, cis-C₄H₈, and 1-C₄H₈) molecules in the optimized geometry, $E[\text{NO}]$ and $E[\text{X}]$ are the energies of the adsorbates in the gas phase, $E[\text{Rh}^+/\text{Zeo}]$ is the energy of the initial zeolite system containing a bare Rh⁺ cation. Consistent with this definition, negative values of BE imply a favorable interaction.

The vibrational frequencies for periodic models were obtained from a normal mode analysis where the elements of the Hessian were approximated as finite differences of gradients, displacing each atomic center by $1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ \AA}$ either way along each Cartesian direction. A partial vibrational Hessian analysis was performed including the atoms from the adsorbates and the rhodium center.

2.6. Catalytic measurements. Catalytic activity measurements for the hydrogenation of C₂H₄ were performed in a quartz single-pass fixed-bed reactor at atmospheric pressure and room temperature. The temperature inside the reactor was monitored by a thermocouple extended into the catalyst bed. Samples in powder form (0.1 g) were loaded in a glovebox and the reactor was sealed to avoid air exposure. The total volumetric flow rate of the reactant mixture (608 Torr H₂/ 76 Torr C₂H₄/balance N₂) was held at 100 ml/min (1atm, 25°C), yielding

a corresponding Gas Hourly Space Velocity (GHSV) of 20,000 h⁻¹. Under these conditions, differential conversions of C₂H₄ (i.e., below 3%) were observed. The feed and the reaction products were analyzed with an on-line gas chromatograph (HP 7890 A, Agilent) equipped with TCD and FID detectors and two capillary columns. An Rt-Alumina column (50m, 0.53 mm ID, Restek) was used for the analysis of hydrocarbons, while a Carboxen 1010 Plot column (30m, 0.53 mm ID, Supelco) was used for the analysis of hydrogen. In the absence of a catalyst, there was no measurable conversion of C₂H₄ in the reactor system.

2.7. X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). XAS spectra were collected at X-ray beamline 4-1 of the Stanford Synchrotron Radiation Laboratory (SSRL), Stanford Linear Accelerator Center, Menlo Park, CA. The storage ring electron energy was 3 GeV and the ring current was in the range of 495-500 mA.

XAS measurements were used to characterize the surface species formed in the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 material. Prior to these measurements, each powder sample was pressed into a wafer inside a N₂-filled glovebox. The sample mass was calculated to give an absorbance of approximately 2.5 at the Rh *K* absorption edge. The pressed sample was loaded into an EXAFS cell,⁴⁵ sealed under N₂, and removed from the glovebox. The cell was evacuated at 10⁻⁵ Torr and aligned in the X-ray beam. The XAS data were collected at liquid nitrogen temperature in the transmission mode with a Si(220) double crystal monochromator that was detuned by 30% to minimize effects of higher harmonics in the X-ray beam. Samples were scanned at energies near the Rh *K* absorption edge (23220 eV). All spectra were calibrated with respect to Rh foil, the spectrum of which was collected simultaneously.

2.8. Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) data analysis. The EXAFS data were analyzed with experimentally determined reference files obtained from EXAFS data characterizing materials of known structure. The Rh–Rh and Rh–O_{support} contributions were analyzed with phase shifts and backscattering amplitudes obtained from EXAFS data for Rh foil and Rh₂O₃, respectively. Reference files for the Rh–N and Rh–O* contributions originating from nitrosyl ligands were obtained from EXAFS data characterizing crystalline Rh(NO)(PPh₃)₃ with the structure described elsewhere.⁴⁶ The RhAl and RhSi interactions were analyzed with phase shifts and backscattering amplitudes calculated with FEFF 7.0 on the basis of the crystallographic data reported for corresponding bulk alloys.^{47,48} The parameters used to extract these files from the EXAFS data were reported elsewhere.^{49,50} The EXAFS data were extracted from the spectra with the XDAP software developed by XAFS Services International.⁵¹ The EXAFS function for each sample was obtained from the X-ray absorption

spectrum by a cubic spline background subtraction and normalized by dividing the absorption intensity by the height of the absorption edge. The final normalized EXAFS function for each sample was obtained from an average of six scans.

The parameters characterizing both low- Z and high- Z contributions were determined by multiple-shell fitting with a maximum of 20 free parameters in r (distance from the absorbing atom, Rh) and k (wave vector) space over the ranges of $0.5 < r < 3.5 \text{ \AA}$ and $3.5 < k < 15.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, respectively, and with application of k^1 and k^3 weighting of the Fourier transform. The statistically justified number of free parameters (n) estimated from the Nyquist theorem (i.e., $n = (2\Delta k\Delta r/\pi) + 1$, where Δk and Δr are the k and r ranges used to fit the data)^{52,53} was approximately 23. The fit was optimized by use of a difference file technique, with phase- and amplitude-corrected Fourier transforms.^{54,55} The best fit parameters determined for each sample examined are summarized in appropriate tables, while comparisons of the data and fits in k and r space are shown in Figs. S1-S5 (supporting information). Standard deviations reported for the various parameters were calculated with the XDAP software, as described elsewhere.⁵⁶ Systematic errors are not included in the calculation of the standard deviations. The values of the goodness of fit (χ^2_ν) were calculated with the XDAP software as outlined in the Reports on Standards and Criteria in XAFS Spectroscopy.⁵⁷ The variances in both the imaginary and absolute parts were used to determine the quality of the fit.⁵⁸

2.9. High Resolution Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy. High resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (HRSTEM) imaging was performed at the University of South Carolina Electron Microscopy Center using a JEOL 2100F 200kV FEG-STEM/TEM microscope equipped with a CEOS C_s corrector on the illumination system. The geometrical aberrations were measured and controlled to provide less than a $\pi/4$ phase shift of the incoming electron wave over the probe-defining aperture of 17.5 mrad. High angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images were acquired with a Fischione Model 3000 HAADF detector at a camera length such that the inner cut-off angle of the detector was 50 mrad. The scanning acquisition was synchronized to the 60 Hz AC electrical power to minimize 60 Hz noise in the images and a pixel dwell time of 15.8 μs was used. Typically, a small quantity of each powder sample was placed on a carbon-coated 200 mesh copper grid and the sample was imaged without any further preparation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Interaction of Rh(CO)₂/HY with NO. The reaction of Rh(CO)₂(acac) complexes with faujasite surfaces has been examined extensively in the past and attributed to the protonation and removal of the acac ligands from these complexes by acidic OH groups of the faujasite, yielding Rh(CO)₂ species anchored to the zeolite framework.^{17-19,34} EXAFS data included in these literature reports for Rh(CO)₂/HY materials thus formed show that the structure of the Rh(CO)₂ moieties remains essentially unchanged upon anchoring because the faujasite surface chelates these species and acts as a bidentate ligand. Therefore, facile substitution of the acac ligand in Rh(CO)₂(acac) by the zeolite support yields supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes which are well-defined, site-isolated, and mononuclear in nature.

There are several known examples for the substitution of CO with NO ligands in organometallic Rh complexes in solution. For example, square-planar [Rh(CO)(PPh₃)₂Cl] complexes can react with NO in CHCl₃ solution to yield 5-coordinated square pyramidal [Rh(NO)₂(PPh₃)₂Cl] complexes.⁵⁹ NO/CO ligand exchange reactions can also take place in supported rhodium complexes, but appear to be strongly affected by the nature of the support. For example, it has been shown that SiO₂-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes prepared from Rh(C₃H₅)₃ do not react with NO at room temperature and form Rh oxide-type species at elevated temperatures (i.e., 100°C).⁶⁰ In contrast, γ-Al₂O₃-supported Rh(CO)₂Cl complexes react with NO at 25°C to form Rh(NO)₂Cl intermediates, which are further converted into RhCl(NO)⁻ species.³⁶ Similarly, FTIR results for highly dealuminated HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ species prepared from [Rh(NH₃)₅Cl](OH)₂ show that their exposure to NO at room temperature yields Rh(NO)₂ complexes.³⁷

To build upon these previous reports, a Rh(CO)₂(acac) precursor was used to prepare a Rh(CO)₂/HY30 material that was extensively characterized by FTIR and EXAFS to establish the uniformity and single-site nature of the surface Rh(CO)₂ complexes formed.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

Figure 1. Difference FTIR spectra illustrating changes in the ν_{CO} and ν_{NO} regions after (1) a pulse of NO over a $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY30}$ sample and (2) a subsequent pulse of CO.

When this $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY30}$ sample was further exposed to a pulse of a 1% NO/He mixture at 25°C, significant changes were observed in the FTIR spectra, as depicted in Fig. 1. More specifically, the ν_{CO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species (i.e., 2117 and 2053 cm^{-1}) disappeared after a 3 min pulse of NO, while new ν_{NO} bands appeared at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1, spectrum 1), indicating the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes. These ν_{NO} bands can be assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric vibrations of new NO ligands⁶¹ and are similar to those previously observed for ZSM-5-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ dinitrosyl complexes (i.e., at 1862 and 1785 cm^{-1}), the structure of which has been confirmed by $^{14}\text{NO}/^{15}\text{NO}$ exchange and DFT calculations.³³ DFT calculations also predict that NO binds 41 kJ/mol stronger than CO to Rh^+ cations^{18,33} and this difference drives the conversion of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ into $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species. Furthermore, CO was immediately detected in the gas phase by MS when the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY30}$ sample was exposed to a pulse of NO at 25°C (Fig. S6, supporting information), consistent with facile substitution of CO ligands by NO.

Even though NO binds to rhodium stronger than CO,^{18,33} several literature examples show that carbonylation of molecular and supported organometallic nitrosyl complexes of rhodium is also possible. For example, it has been reported that the treatment of $[\text{Rh}(\text{PPH}_3)_2(\text{NO})_2]\text{ClO}_4$

in acetone solution with CO yields $[\text{Rh}(\text{PPH}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]\text{ClO}_4$.⁶² Likewise, $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})\text{Cl}$ complexes were transformed into $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}$ species following treatment with CO.³⁶ Similarly, the CO-NO exchange appears to be reversible over the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY30}$ material examined. When the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$ sample was exposed to a 3 min pulse of a 1% CO/He mixture, the difference FTIR spectra shown in Fig. 1 (spectrum 2) demonstrate that the ν_{NO} bands of the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes disappeared completely, while the ν_{CO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species were restored. Furthermore, the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ transformation cycles could be repeated several times without any loss of infrared band intensities in either the ν_{CO} or ν_{NO} regions, suggesting that the substitution of the CO/NO ligands proceed to completion every time and no agglomeration of the Rh sites takes place. MS data (Fig. S6, supporting information) for gas phase products reinforce this point even further, as the sequential NO/CO pulses steadily generate corresponding CO/NO signals of the same intensity, consistent with full quantitative replacement of CO by NO and vice versa.

3.1.1 Effect of Al content. To determine if $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species can be also formed on HY zeolites with a higher Al content, $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY15}$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY2.6}$ samples prepared from the $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$ precursor were exposed to a 1% NO/He mixture at 25°C. Similar to the case of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY30}$, the treatment of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY15}$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2/\text{HY2.6}$ with NO results in the quick disappearance of the ν_{CO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes and the simultaneous appearance of the ν_{NO} vibrations of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species. Regardless of the zeolite used, the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes thus formed were found to be stable for an extended period of time under He flow. Figs. 2A-2C show the FTIR spectra in the ν_{NO} region for all samples examined. From these data, it is evident that the symmetric and asymmetric ν_{NO} vibrations of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species appear in all cases at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating that the position of these bands does not depend on the Al content.

Recently, we have shown that the interaction of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$ with dealuminated HY zeolites results in the formation of two different types of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species with characteristic ν_{CO} bands at 2117/2053 and 2110/2043 cm^{-1} .¹⁸ While the position of these ν_{CO} bands does not depend on the Si/Al ratio of zeolites used, the fraction of each species formed strongly depends on the Al content, with more species of the second type observed on zeolites with lower Si/Al ratios. For example, the relative fraction of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species with the ν_{CO} bands at 2110/2043 cm^{-1} is approximately 17% in the case of HY30, increasing to 40 and 50% in the case of HY15 and HY2.6 zeolites, respectively. Our previous results also indicate that neither type of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species formed can be linked to unreacted or partially reacted $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})$

complexes or to the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x$ species. Instead, DFT calculations have shown that differences in the nature of binding sites in dealuminated faujasites are responsible for the formation of these species.¹⁸ Since the replacement of carbonyl ligands in supported $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes by NO is a facile substitution process, one could also expect similar formation of at least two types of zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes.

Figure 2. Room-temperature FTIR spectra in the ν_{NO} region of (A) $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$, (B) $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY15}$, and (C) $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY2.6}$ samples (solid line) and deconvolution results (dashed lines).

Indeed, the ν_{NO} bands of zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes are fairly broad (Figs. 2A-2C and Table 1). Furthermore, both ν_{NO} bands in the spectrum of the sample with the largest Al content (Fig. 2C) are asymmetric at the low-frequency side, indicating the formation of more than one type of supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes. The deconvolution results also shown in Fig. 2C confirm this point, as two pairs of ν_{NO} bands can be clearly identified at 1856/1780 and 1846/1758 cm^{-1} , consistent with two different types of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes being formed in this case. Similar to what was observed for $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ species,¹⁸ the presence of different $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes on zeolites with a smaller Al content is not immediately apparent from the shape of the ν_{NO} bands (Figs. 2A and 2B). However, our attempts to fit these spectra with one pair of bands and acceptable coefficients of determination (R^2) were not successful, as fits with R^2 above 0.95 were obtained only when two components for each ν_{NO} band were included in the fit. Based on the deconvolution results shown in Figs. 2A and 2B, it is evident that two different types of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species can be also identified on HY30 and HY15 zeolites.

$\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species with the ν_{NO} bands at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} constitute the majority of the surface species formed on all three zeolites (Table 1). While the relative fraction of these species varies from 82 to 91%, depending on the zeolite used, such an increase is too small to

confidently support any correlations with the Al content of the zeolite. Furthermore, regardless of the zeolite used, the dinitrosyl species formed have the same ν_{NO} bands, N-Rh-N angles (104°), and ($\nu_{\text{s}}-\nu_{\text{as}}$) splits (76 cm^{-1}), suggesting that these complexes have the same structure on all zeolites examined.

Table 1. Deconvolution parameters for the ν_{NO} bands observed in FTIR spectra of various $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}$ samples.

Sample	Band position, cm^{-1}	FWHM, cm^{-1}	Split ($\nu_{\text{s}}-\nu_{\text{as}}$), ^a cm^{-1}	N-Rh-N angle, deg	Relative fraction, %
$\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$	1855	13.6	76	104	91
	1779	19.0			
	1845	10.0	76	106	9
	1769	17.2			
$\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY15}$	1855	12.4	76	104	85
	1779	18.0			
	1846	10.2	77	106	15
	1769	16.8			
$\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY2.6}$	1856	17.4	76	104	82
	1780	21.1			
	1846	23.2	88	106	18
	1758	24.2			

^aThe “s” and “as” subscripts refer to symmetric and asymmetric vibrations, respectively.

The second type of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes with the ν_{NO} bands at lower frequencies constitutes the minority of the surface species formed, as the relative fraction of these species varies in the 10-18% range (Table 1). Once again, the difference is too small to link these species with confidence to the Al content. Regardless of the zeolite used, the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species of this type have the same N-Rh-N angles (106°) and symmetric ν_{NO} vibrations at 1846 cm^{-1} . However, the position of the asymmetric ν_{NO} component shifts from 1758 to 1769 cm^{-1} as the Si/Al ratio increases from 2.6 to 15 and remains unchanged thereafter (Table 1). It is not clear at the moment as to why the split between symmetric and asymmetric ν_{NO} vibrations for this type of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species becomes smaller with dealumination, but the results obtained were found to be highly reproducible.

When these FTIR data are further combined with those reported previously for $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes on similar zeolites,¹⁸ it becomes evident that two types of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes can be identified on each zeolite examined. In the dicarbonyl case, however, the fraction of type II species strongly correlates with the Al content, while there is no such correlation for dinitrosyls. Therefore, one can assume that the type II $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species are not

formed directly upon exposure to NO from the type II Rh(CO)₂ ones and that the nature of these Rh(NO)₂ species is somewhat different.

Table 2. EXAFS structural parameters characterizing surface species formed on the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample.^a

Sample	Shell	N	R (Å)	$\Delta\sigma^2$ (Å ²)	ΔE_0 (eV)	χ^2_ν	k^1 -variances (%)	
							Im.	Abs.
Rh(NO) ₂ /HY30	Rh–Rh	--	--	--	--	1.5	0.5	0.4
	Rh–N*	1.9	1.77	-0.00157	-2.2			
	Rh–O*	1.7	2.83	0.00960	2.9			
	Rh–support							
	Rh–O	1.9	2.30	0.00573	-3.2			
	Rh–Al	0.8	3.12	0.00066	-3.8			
	Rh–Si	0.4	3.61	-0.00309	-6.4			

Notations: *N*, coordination number; *R*, distance between absorber and backscatterer atoms; $\Delta\sigma^2$, Debye-Waller factor relative to the Debye-Waller factor of the reference compound; ΔE_0 , inner potential correction accounting for the difference in the inner potential between the sample and the reference compound; χ^2_ν , goodness of fit; the superscript * refers to nitrosyl ligands. Standard deviations in fits: $N \pm 20\%$, $R \pm 1\%$, $\Delta\sigma^2 \pm 10\%$, $\Delta E_0 \pm 10\%$. ^a *R*-space fit ranges $3.5 < k < 15.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and $0.5 < r < 4.0 \text{ \AA}$; 26 allowed fitting parameters.

3.2 Structural properties of supported Rh(NO)₂ species. Since the FTIR data collected for the Rh(NO)₂/HY30, Rh(NO)₂/HY15, and Rh(NO)₂/HY2.6 samples were found to be similar, only the former was examined by EXAFS. Structural parameters determined by fitting the raw EXAFS spectra of this sample are summarized in Table 2, while comparisons of the data and fits are shown in Figs. S1-S5 (supporting information). Overall, the results indicate that the replacement of CO ligands in Rh(CO)₂/HY30 by NO does not change substantially the nature of the Rh sites. More specifically, the absence of Rh–Rh contributions in the EXAFS spectra of Rh(NO)₂/HY30 indicates that the Rh surface species remain site-isolated and mononuclear in nature. Furthermore, the presence of Rh–N and Rh–O* contributions with average coordination numbers of 1.9 and 1.7 at average bond distances of 1.77 and 2.83 Å, respectively, indicates that approximately two NO ligands are bound to each Rh atom and, therefore, these mononuclear Rh complexes can be approximated as Rh(NO)₂ dinitrosyls.

However, some structural differences between HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ and Rh(NO)₂ complexes are also apparent. For example, the contributions from the NO ligands in the EXAFS spectra of Rh(NO)₂/HY30 have shorter Rh–N and Rh–O* bond distances than the Rh–C and Rh–O* distances reported for zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes with carbonyl ligands linearly bound to Rh sites,¹⁸ suggesting that the overall geometry of Rh(NO)₂ species is somewhat different. The observed Rh–N bond distance of 1.77 Å falls in the 1.60-1.90 Å

range, which is typical of terminal nitrosyl ligands in coordination complexes and clusters of various transition metals, including Rh.⁶¹ For example, a Rh–N bond distance of 1.76 Å has been reported in the case of pincer-type Rh(PCP'Bu)(NO)[BF₄] complexes incorporating only one nitrosyl ligand.⁶³ In contrast to the CO ligands, terminal nitrosyl ligands in coordination complexes and clusters of various transition metals can assume linear and bent configurations with typical M–N–O bond angles varying between 180–160° and 140–110°, respectively.⁶¹ Based on the Rh–N and Rh–O* bond distances determined by EXAFS and taking into account that terminal nitrosyls have an average N–O distance of 1.17 Å,⁶¹ one can calculate that M–N–O bond angles in the HY zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes are approximately 148°, which is in line with our theoretical data (Tables 3 and 4). This angle represents a borderline region for linear and bent NO forms and indicates that the NO ligands of Rh(NO)₂/HY30 significantly deviate from a linear geometry. This result is consistent with previous literature reports demonstrating that the NO ligands of Rh(NO)₂/ZSM-5 are bent with respect to the lines determined by the Rh ion and the two zeolite oxygen atoms bound to it.³³

The Rh-support interactions are characterized by the presence of Rh–O contributions with an average coordination number of 1.9 at an average bond distance of 2.30 Å (Table 2). Since an average Rh–O coordination number of approximately 2 was also observed for Rh(CO)₂/HY30, we can conclude that the zeolite support continues to chelate Rh(NO)₂ moieties and act as a bidentate ligand after facile substitution of CO ligands with NO. In this case, however, the Rh–O distance is significantly longer than that between Rh and the two zeolite oxygen atoms of Rh(CO)₂/HY30 (i.e., 2.14 Å).¹⁸ This result can be attributed to the stronger trans-influence of NO ligands as compared to CO.⁶⁴

Finally, DFT calculations reported elsewhere³⁴ for the case of dealuminated Y zeolites predict coordination of Rh(CO)₂ moieties near Al cations of the zeolite framework with expected Rh–Al distances on the order of 2.8 Å. Experimental EXAFS data reported for zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes confirm this prediction, as Rh–Al contributions have been often included in the fitting routine and average coordination numbers and distances obtained for them were found to be in the 0.6–1.3 and 2.74–3.39 Å ranges, respectively.^{12,34,65} Consistent with these literature reports, Rh–Al and Rh–Si contributions with average coordination numbers of 0.8 and 0.4 at average bond distances of 3.12 and 3.61 Å, respectively, were identified in the EXAFS spectra of the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample (Table 2). Including these two contributions in the analysis was necessary, since the overall fit of the raw data was not

satisfactory in their absence. Furthermore, comparisons of the data and fits in r space with application of k^1 and k^3 weighting of the Fourier transform shown in Figs. S4 and S5 (supporting information) provide a strong basis for the assignment of these two contributions to the high-Z backscatterers.⁵⁸ While it is evident that Al and Si backscatterers located at such long distances are not bound directly to Rh by chemical bonds, the presence of Rh–Al and Rh–Si contributions in the EXAFS spectrum of Rh(NO)₂/HY30 implies that there is no migration of Rh atoms over the zeolite surface during conversion of Rh(CO)₂ complexes into Rh(NO)₂ species, as oxygen atoms coordinated to Al³⁺ cations continue to represent the binding sites for Rh(NO)₂ species in the zeolite framework.

3.3 Modeling of supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes. To further examine the nature of faujasite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes and to provide specific assignments for the infrared bands observed, periodic DFT calculations were performed. Such calculations take into account the whole zeolite framework and provide information on the local structure and stability of the species formed in zeolite cavities.^{66,67} The approach used in this case was similar to that applied previously for HY zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes.¹⁸ As shown in Fig. 3, Rh⁺(NO)₂ complexes located in the cavity of the highly dealuminated faujasite structure can be potentially attached to three different pairs of oxygen atoms located at the AlO₄⁻ tetrahedron, all of which are accessible from the supercage. To distinguish between these three oxygen pairs involved in the anchoring of the Rh species, the supported Rh⁺(NO)₂ complexes are denoted in the same way (i.e., as Rh(NO)_{2_a}, Rh(NO)_{2_b}, and Rh(NO)_{2_c}) as corresponding dicarbonyl species in Ref. 18. In the case of Rh(NO)_{2_a} complexes, the anchoring oxygen atoms are from two different but coupled four-membered rings, while in the case of Rh(NO)_{2_b} and Rh(NO)_{2_c} species, both oxygen atoms belong to the same four- and six-membered ring, respectively. The calculation results for all these structures are summarized in Tables 3 and 4.

The results shown in Table 3 indicate that the Rh(NO)_{2_a} complex is the most stable one, with a binding energy of both NO ligands of -555 kJ/mol. Furthermore, this complex is more stable by 41 kJ/mol than the corresponding Rh(CO)_{2_a} dicarbonyl complex.¹⁸

Rh(NO)₂_a

Rh(NO)₂_b

Rh(NO)₂_c

Rh(NO)₂_a_Al₂

Rh(NO)₂_b_Al₂

Rh(NO)₂_a_Al₂_no_HB

Rh(NO)₂_a_Al₂'

Rh(NO)₂(H)_a

Rh(NO)₂(H₂)_a

Figure 3. Optimized local structures of all faujasite-supported complexes (the full zeolite structure is not shown for clarity). The zeolite fragment is represented by sticks. Color coding: gray – Si; red – O; green – Al; brown – N; yellow – C; white – H; blue – Rh.

Table 3. Calculated binding energies (BE in kJ/mol) for all ligands (NO, H₂, C₂H₄, 1/2H₂, C₄H₈), N-O and Rh-H vibrational frequencies (in cm⁻¹) and comparison with experimental values. The difference between calculated and experimentally observed vibrational frequencies is also given, $\Delta = \nu^{\text{calc}} - \nu^{\text{exp}}$ (in cm⁻¹).

	BE	BE ^a	RE ^c	RE-D ^c	$\nu(\text{N-O})^{\text{calc}}$	$\nu(\text{N-O})^{\text{calc}}$	$\nu(\text{N-O})^{\text{exp}}$	$\nu(\text{N-O})^{\text{exp}}$	Δ	Δ	$\nu(\text{Rh-H})^{\text{calc}}$
Rh(NO) ₂ _a	-555		0	0	1855	1780	1855	1779	0	1	
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Ns_2	-459		104		1782	1710					
Rh(NO) ₂ _b	-523		32	30	1858	1792					
Rh(NO) ₂ _c	-527		28	32	1857	1788					
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂	-542		21		1833	1725	1845	1769	-12	-44	
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂ _no_HB	-548		15		1856	1778					
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂ '	-538		25		1861	1790					
Rh(NO) ₂ _b_Al ₂	-524		39		1831	1761	1845	1769	-14	-8	
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₄)_a	-613	-58			1826	1745	1810	1716	16	29	
Rh(NO) ₂ (H)(C ₂ H ₄)_a	-546		74	72	1793	1725	1795	1706	-2	19	
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅)_a	-620		0	0	1788	1724	1795	1706	-7	18	
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₄) ₂ _a	-598	-43	148	130	1763	1694					
Rh(NO) ₂ (tr-C ₄ H ₈)_a	-608	-53	5	1	1813	1734					
Rh(NO) ₂ (cis-C ₄ H ₈)_a	-618	-63	0	0	1802	1731					
Rh(NO) ₂ (1-C ₄ H ₈)_a	-607	-52	22	21	1817	1745					
Rh(NO) ₂ (CH ₂) ₄ _5R_a	-638		108	102	1848	1711					
Rh(NO) ₂ (H)_a	-489	66 ^b	66 ^b	66 ^b	1813	1751					1960
Rh(NO) ₂ (H ₂)_a	-556	-1	-1	-1	1851	1775	1855	1779	-4	-4	

^a The binding energy of the additional ligand(s) in the complex as compared to the Rh(NO)₂_a complex.

^b With respect to a half H₂ molecule.

^c RE and RE-D denote the relative energy of complexes with the same composition calculated without and with accounting of dispersion interactions, respectively.

The binding energies for Rh(NO)₂_b and Rh(NO)₂_c complexes were found to be -523 and -527 kJ/mol, respectively, implying that the stability of zeolite-supported Rh dinitrosyl species declines in the Rh(NO)₂_a > Rh(NO)₂_c > Rh(NO)₂_b order, although the difference in stability of the latter two species is only marginal. This pattern clearly correlates with that established previously for corresponding Rh dicarbonyl complexes.¹⁸ All these Rh dinitrosyl structures have a singlet configuration in which the unpaired electrons of the NO molecules and two d-electrons of the Rh⁺ cation form the Rh–NO bonds (Fig. S7, supporting information, right panel). Therefore, these faujasite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes have zero unpaired electrons, maintain a 14-electron

count, and in the most stable position (i.e., Rh(NO)₂_a), the complex assumes a square-planar geometry when the oxygen atoms of the zeolite and the N atoms of the NO ligands are taken into account. This feature of the complex affects its chemical behavior since the rhodium center has one empty d-orbital that allows for coordination of an additional electron-donating ligand such as C₂H₄. Thus, the key difference between zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ and Rh(NO)₂ species is the electron count. The former are 16-electron species which are not capable of coordinating ethene as an additional ligand. For this reason, ethene replaces one of the CO ligands in zeolite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes.

We also have modeled the most stable Rh(NO)₂_a complex with a triplet configuration and denoted it as Rh(NO)₂_a_Ns_2 in Tables 3 and 4. In this case, each NO ligand donates a lone pair to the Rh⁺ cation to form the Rh–NO bonds and, therefore, the zeolite-supported complex has two unpaired electrons and maintains a 16-electron count (Fig. S7, supporting information, left panel). The results show that the triplet Rh(NO)₂_a_Ns_2 structure is less stable by ~100 kJ/mol than the singlet Rh(NO)₂_a structure. While the Rh–N–O angles in both structures are similar and consistent with the experimental data, the Rh–O_{support} contributions are significantly shorter in the triplet structure (i.e., 2.15–2.18 Å) than the corresponding distances in the singlet structure (i.e., 2.26–2.43 Å) and also those observed experimentally (i.e., 2.30 Å). In addition, the ν_{NO} bands of the triplet structure (i.e., 1782 and 1710 cm⁻¹) are by ~70 cm⁻¹ lower than the corresponding frequencies in the singlet structure and were not observed in the experimental data. Consequently, we can confidently eliminate the possibility of the formation of such a structure in our case and conclude that our experimental structural data are consistent with the formation of more stable Rh(NO)₂ complexes in a singlet configuration.

Indeed, the calculated symmetric and asymmetric ν_{NO} vibrational frequencies for the most stable Rh(NO)₂_a structure are 1855 and 1780 cm⁻¹, respectively (Table 3), and these values match within 1 cm⁻¹ the experimental ν_{NO} bands observed at 1855 and 1779 cm⁻¹. The symmetric ν_{NO} modes of the less stable Rh(NO)₂_b and Rh(NO)₂_c complexes are predicted to appear at 1858 and 1857 cm⁻¹, while the corresponding asymmetric ν_{NO} modes are expected at 1792 and 1788 cm⁻¹, respectively (Table 3). While the DFT calculations predict the possible formation of three types of zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes, the spectral fingerprints of the Rh(NO)₂_b and Rh(NO)₂_c complexes completely overlap in the ν_{NO} region making it impossible to distinguish

between these two species in the experimental FTIR spectra. Moreover, since the experimental ν_{NO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes are relatively wide, with FWHM values varying in the 10-20

Table 4. Selected interatomic distances (in Å) and angles in the optimized structures.

	Rh-O ^b	Rh-O ^c	Rh-Al	Rh-Si	Rh-N	N-O	Rh-C	Rh-N-O
Rh	2.11, 2.14, 2.20							
Rh(NO) ₂ - exp	2.30	2.83	3.12	3.61	1.77			
Rh(NO) ₂ _a	2.26, 2.32	2.85, 2.86	3.07	3.58, 3.62	1.81, 1.81	1.177, 1.176		143.7, 145.7
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Ns_2	2.15, 2.18	2.90, 2.90	2.94	3.52, 3.52	1.87, 1.88	1.186, 1.187		141.3, 141.5
Rh(NO) ₂ _b	2.30, 2.43	2.85, 2.87	2.83	3.46, 3.46	1.81, 1.82	1.173, 1.178		144.0, 147.9
Rh(NO) ₂ _c	2.30, 2.43	2.84, 2.88	2.83	3.57, 3.59	1.81, 1.82	1.175, 1.176		142.1, 148.2
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂	2.23, 2.26	2.85, 2.86	3.05	3.53, 3.58	1.80, 1.81	1.176, 1.191 ^a		142.9, 145.6
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂ _no_HB	2.27, 2.29	2.85, 2.86	3.06	3.54, 3.61	1.81, 1.81	1.175, 1.179		143.7, 145.4
Rh(NO) ₂ _a_Al ₂ '	2.27, 2.34	2.85, 2.87	3.62, 3.64	3.00	1.81, 1.81	1.174, 1.177		144.9, 147.6
Rh(NO) ₂ _b_Al ₂	2.28, 2.38	2.85, 2.87	2.83	3.35, 3.45	1.80, 1.82	1.177, 1.183 ^a		142.3, 147.1
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₄)_a	2.40, 2.51	2.80, 2.88	3.22	3.67, 3.79	1.84, 1.87	1.176, 1.182	2.28, 2.31	132.4, 145.0
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₄) ₂ _a	2.51, 2.82	2.80, 2.80	3.40	3.71, 4.03	1.91, 1.92	1.183, 1.188	2.31, 2.32, 2.66, 2.69	127.1, 127.2
Rh(NO) ₂ (H)(C ₂ H ₄)_a	2.35, 2.49	2.84, 2.86	3.17	3.65, 3.74	1.89, 1.91	1.182, 1.182	2.44, 2.47	131.7, 136.1
Rh(NO) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅)_a	2.29, 2.43	2.86, 2.86	3.12	3.57, 3.71	1.85, 1.86	1.184, 1.184	2.13	138.4, 139.4
Rh(NO) ₂ (tr-C ₄ H ₈)_a	2.44, 2.49	2.80, 2.89	3.23	3.69, 3.76	1.84, 1.86	1.178, 1.185	2.30, 2.37	132.1, 145.6
Rh(NO) ₂ (cis-C ₄ H ₈)_a	2.39, 2.52	2.81, 2.87	3.20	3.65, 3.78	1.84, 1.85	1.180, 1.184	2.34, 2.38	135.0, 142.1
Rh(NO) ₂ (1-C ₄ H ₈)_a	2.39, 2.53				1.84, 1.86	1.178, 1.183	2.30, 2.39	134.9, 143.6
Rh(NO) ₂ (CH ₂) ₄ _5R_a	2.32, 2.58	2.74, 2.94	3.20	3.55, 3.88	1.87, 1.91	1.171, 1.189	2.12, 2.19	122.8, 149.5
Rh(NO) ₂ (H)_a	2.29, 2.33	2.85, 2.88	3.08	3.60, 3.61	1.86, 1.87	1.178, 1.181		141.9, 137.4
Rh(NO) ₂ (H ₂)_a	2.30, 2.38	2.83, 2.87	3.11	3.63, 3.65	1.81, 1.83	1.175, 1.178		139.8, 147.0
Rh(NO)(NOH)_a	2.22, 2.30	2.82, 2.88	3.02	3.56, 3.60	1.82, 1.83	1.181, 1.328		126.9, 145.8
Rh(NO) ₂ _a	2.21, 2.25	2.77, 2.79	2.99	3.55, 3.57	1.83, 1.84	1.331, 1.332		121.3, 122.9
Rh(NO)(NOH)(C ₂ H ₅)_a	2.26, 2.46	2.82, 2.85	3.11	3.56, 3.74	1.81, 1.86	1.186, 1.329	2.12	127.1, 137.4

^aO participates in a hydrogen bond with the OH group; ^bO from the zeolite framework; ^cO from the NO molecule.

cm^{-1} range (Table 1), it is also not possible to distinguish between $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ _a species and those in locations b and c in our FTIR spectra, since the difference in the position of the symmetric and asymmetric ν_{NO} bands of all these species is 2-3 cm^{-1} and 8-12 cm^{-1} , respectively. Finally, the calculated positions for the ν_{NO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ _b and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ _c are shifted to higher frequencies as compare to those of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ _a (Table 3), indicating that the former two species

cannot be responsible for the additional ν_{NO} bands observed experimentally at 1845 and 1769 cm^{-1} . However, we can conclude with confidence that the dominant ν_{NO} bands at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} represent a group of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes located at positions a, b, and c in the zeolite framework.

To further explore the origin of the ν_{NO} bands observed in the FTIR spectra at 1845 and 1769 cm^{-1} , we have modeled two additional Rh dinitrosyl type “a” and “b” complexes located at the region with two Al centers being present in the unit cell and forming O-Al-O-Si-O-Al sequences. These species are denoted as $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_b_Al_2$ in Fig. 3 and Table 3. The second Al center is compensated by a H^+ that forms a bridging OH group. In these two complexes, the bridging OH group forms a weak hydrogen bond with one of the NO ligands, where the distances between the H atom from the OH group and the O atom from the NO ligand are 2.01 and 2.38 Å for the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_b_Al_2$ complexes, respectively. The results shown in Table 3 indicate that hydrogen bonding down shifts both ν_{NO} frequencies by $\sim 20\text{-}50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in respect to those of the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_b$ complexes with only one Al center in the unit cell. Therefore, the presence of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_b_Al_2$ complexes may eventually explain the appearance of the second set of ν_{NO} bands in the FTIR spectra at 1845 and 1769 cm^{-1} , but the calculated shift is larger than the experimental one.

To determine whether the hydrogen bonding is responsible for the shift of the ν_{NO} frequencies or the presence of a second Al center alone is sufficient, we have also modeled a structure (denoted as $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2_no_HB$) with two Al centers in which the compensating H^+ cation is moved to another O atom, so that the formation of a hydrogen bond with the NO ligands becomes impossible. In this case, the calculated ν_{NO} frequencies were found to be 1856 and 1778 cm^{-1} , which differ by only 2 cm^{-1} from those calculated for the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a$ structure with only one Al center. The BE of NO in the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2_no_HB$ complexes is lower as an absolute value by only 13-7 kJ/mol than that in the most stable $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a$ complex with only one Al center.

Finally, we have also made the assumption that the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complex interacts with two O atoms from the middle O-Si-O fragment, while both of these oxygens are also bound to one of the two Al centers (Fig. 3). The BE of NO ligands in this structure (denoted as $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2'$) is lower as an absolute value by only 10 kJ/mol than the corresponding value of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a_Al_2_no_HB$, while the calculated ν_{NO} frequencies were 1861 and 1790 cm^{-1} (Table 3), approximately 10 cm^{-1} higher than the corresponding ν_{NO} frequencies of the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a$ and

Rh(NO)₂_a_Al₂_no_HB structures. Consequently, the formation of this specific type of complex also cannot explain the experimental results. Therefore, our modelling results suggest that weak hydrogen bonding between surface OH groups and NO ligands is most likely responsible for the appearance of low frequency ν_{NO} bands at 1845 and 1769 cm⁻¹ in the experimental FTIR spectra, which are the most prominent in the case of HY2.6 zeolite.

3.4 Interaction of Rh⁺(NO)₂/HY30 with H₂. As we have reported elsewhere,¹⁷⁻¹⁹ the faujasite-supported Rh(CO)₂ complexes do not react with hydrogen at room temperature. It appears that faujasite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes have similar chemical properties with respect to hydrogen. Indeed, the flow of H₂ over Rh(NO)₂/HY30 at 25°C does not lead to any changes in the FTIR spectra (Fig. S8 (spectra 1 and 2), supporting information). The same result was obtained when the temperature or the hydrogen pressure in the FTIR cell were increased to 90°C and 45 psi, respectively (Fig. S8 (spectra 3 and 4), supporting information).

These observations are further supported by DFT calculations. Hydrogen-containing derivatives of the most stable Rh(NO)₂_a dinitrosyls were modeled, including the Rh(NO)₂(H₂)_a complex incorporating molecular hydrogen, the Rh(NO)₂(H)₂_a complex incorporating dissociated H₂, and the Rh(NO)₂(H)_a complex incorporating only one H atom (Tables 3 and 4).

The Rh(NO)₂(H)₂_a complex is unstable and transforms into the Rh(NO)₂(H₂)_a one during the geometry optimization procedure. In the latter species, however, the H₂ ligand is essentially desorbed because the Rh–H distances are on the order of 2.38 Å and its binding energy is only -1 kJ/mol. As a result, changes in positions of the ν_{NO} bands are small (i.e., ~5 cm⁻¹) compared to the ν_{NO} bands of the Rh(NO)₂_a complex. For the Rh(NO)₂(H)_a complex, the ν_{NO} vibrational frequencies are 1813 and 1751 cm⁻¹ and the calculated Rh–H frequency is 1960 cm⁻¹. However, this complex is unstable compared to the combination of Rh(NO)₂_a and half H₂ molecule in gas phase by 66 kJ/mol. Overall, these calculation results are consistent with the experimental observations and indicate that hydrogen does not interact strong enough with dinitrosyl complexes.

3.5 Interaction of Rh⁺(NO)₂/HY30 with C₂H₄. In contrast to the hydrogen, the carbonyl ligands of zeolite-bound Rh(CO)₂ complexes readily react with gas phase C₂H₄ to form Rh(CO)(C₂H₄) species.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ In spite of the structural similarity of faujasite-supported Rh(CO)₂ and Rh(NO)₂ complexes, we have found that the 14-electron Rh(NO)₂ complexes exhibit a different type of surface chemistry.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra in the ν_{NO} region of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$ after sequential exposure to flows of (1) He, (2) C_2H_4 , and (3) He at 25°C for 15 min.

For example, the ν_{NO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ surface species originally observed under the He flow at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} shifted to 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} , respectively, when the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$ sample was exposed to C_2H_4 flow for approximately 15 min (Fig. 4, spectra 1 and 2). During this period, significant changes were also observed in the ν_{OH} and ν_{CH} regions. The ν_{OH} band of silanols⁶⁸ located at 3744 cm^{-1} declined in intensity, while a new broad ν_{OH} band appeared at 3635 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5). A number of new bands also appeared in the ν_{CH} region (Fig. 6). While most of these ν_{CH} bands overlap with each other, their maxima can be clearly identified at 3015 , 2966 , 2937 , 2924 , 2892 , 2879 , and 2864 cm^{-1} without deconvolution. The changes observed in the ν_{OH} and ν_{CH} regions reflect primarily C_2H_4 -zeolite interactions. For example, the formation of hydrogen bonds between C_2H_4 and silanols explains the changes observed in the ν_{OH} region, while the interaction of C_2H_4 with acidic hydroxyls yields CH_3CH_2^+ species with characteristic ν_{CO} vibrations in the $2966\text{--}2864\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region.⁶⁹

Figure 5. Difference FTIR spectra illustrating changes in the ν_{OH} region after exposure of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$ to a C_2H_4 flow at 25°C for (1) 1 min, (2) 5 min, and (3) 15 min.

However, the most important observation is the appearance of the 3015 cm^{-1} band that represents the ν_{CH_2} vibrations of C_2H_4 species π -bonded to Rh sites.⁷⁰ Since zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ is formally a 14-electron complex, it can coordinate an additional 2-electron donor ligand such as C_2H_4 to form 16-electron $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species. Furthermore, since π -bonded C_2H_4 increases the electron density on Rh, a shift of the ν_{NO} bands of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ complexes to lower frequencies is expected, consistent with our experimental observations.

Figure 6. Difference FTIR spectrum illustrating changes in the ν_{CH} region after exposure of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$ to a C_2H_4 flow at 25°C for 15 min.

As soon as the C_2H_4 flow was stopped and replaced with He, the ν_{NO} bands at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} disappeared and the ν_{NO} bands of the original $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes reappeared with the same intensity at 1855 and 1779 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4, spectrum 3). Furthermore, all ν_{CH} bands completely disappeared from the spectra along with the hydrogen-bonded ν_{OH} vibrations at 3635 cm^{-1} , while the silanol band reappeared at 3744 cm^{-1} (Fig. 7, spectrum 2). All spectral changes observed under the He flow were found to be completely reversible, as a subsequent cycle of C_2H_4 flow restored all ν_{CH} bands shown in Fig. 6, the changes in the ν_{OH} region (Fig. 7, spectrum 3), and the ν_{NO} bands at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} . Overall, these results indicate a weak and completely reversible coordination of C_2H_4 to both the support and the Rh sites.

DFT calculations were performed to further examine the structure of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species using a $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_a$ complex (Fig. 3). The results summarized in Tables 3 and 4 show that the binding energy of ethene in this complex is -58 kJ/mol (-92 kJ/mol when dispersion correction is taken into account, Table S1) and that a ν_{NO} vibrational frequency shift is expected towards lower frequencies. However, the calculated ν_{NO} values of 1826 and 1745 cm^{-1} are by 16 and 29 cm^{-1} higher than the ν_{NO} bands experimentally observed at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} . The reasons for

these differences are not clear to us at this point. Calculations were also performed with a complex containing two ethene ligands, $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$, but the results (Tables 3 and 4, S1 in SI) indicate that coordination of the second ethene molecule by the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ species is less favorable energetically than the first one even when dispersion interaction is taken into account in the calculations (by 56 kJ/mol). Such complex is most likely not formed at all since the ν_{NO} bands of this species do not fit the experimental data within a reasonable proximity range.

Figure 7. Difference FTIR spectra illustrating changes in the ν_{OH} region after subsequent 5 min exposures of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}30$ at 25°C to (1) C_2H_4 , (2) He, and (3) C_2H_4 flow.

Finally, the data presented above show a significant difference in reactivity of HY zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes towards C_2H_4 . In the case of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$, one of the two carbonyl ligands is selectively replaced with C_2H_4 to form $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ In contrast, C_2H_4 does not replace a nitrosyl ligand in the case of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ but rather coordinates to Rh to yield $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species. This is a clear example that demonstrates how the subtle electronic differences of the CO and NO ligands affect the chemical properties of the coordinating Rh sites.

3.6 Interaction of Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄)/HY30 with H₂. As we have reported previously,^{17,19} the Rh(CO)(C₂H₄)/HY30 sample readily reacts with H₂ at 25°C to yield Rh(CO)(H)_x species on the zeolite surface. To determine if the most stable Rh(NO)₂(H₂)_a complexes can be potentially formed with the Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄)/HY30 material, interactions of this sample with H₂ were examined. In contrast to the Rh(CO)(C₂H₄) complexes, which were found to be stable under the He flow, the Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄) species incorporate weakly bound C₂H₄ and exist only when C₂H₄ is present in the gas phase. Therefore, we have used a modified procedure for this type of measurements. In a first step, the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample was exposed to C₂H₄ at 25°C to form Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄) complexes with characteristic ν_{NO} bands at 1810 and 1716 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 8, spectrum 1). When this step was completed, C₂H₄ was replaced with a 75% H₂/25% C₂H₄ mixture and FTIR spectra were collected as a function of time on stream until no further changes were observed in the spectra.

Figure 8. FTIR spectra in the ν_{NO} region of Rh(NO)₂/HY30 after exposure to flows of (1) C₂H₄ and a 75% H₂/25% C₂H₄ mixture at 25°C for (2) 1 min, (3) 5 min, (4) 9 min, and (5) 60 min.

Significant changes were observed in the ν_{NO} region upon addition of H_2 to the C_2H_4 flow (Fig. 8, spectra 2-5). More specifically, the ν_{NO} bands at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} , characteristic of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ complexes, progressively declined in intensity, while two new ν_{NO} bands developed at 1795 and 1706 cm^{-1} . The development of the latter bands was completed after approximately 60 min on stream, while the ν_{NO} bands at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} have completely disappeared at that time. Subsequent flow of He does not affect significantly the position and intensity of the ν_{NO} bands at 1795 and 1706 cm^{-1} , implying that the surface species formed are sufficiently stable.

Apparently, we did not detect any ν_{NO} bands at 1851 and 1775 cm^{-1} that can be assigned to $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{H}_2)_a$ complexes (Table 3), indicating that there is no simple path to the formation of rhodium hydrides not only from $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ but also from $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species as well. This result once again supports the previous conclusion that the subtle electronic changes induced by CO and NO ligands to zeolite-supported single rhodium sites significantly change the reactivity of these sites and pathways to activation of simple molecules like C_2H_4 and H_2 . However, since zeolite-supported $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})(\text{H})_x$ species readily react with C_2H_4 to yield C_2H_6 in the gas phase,¹⁹ one could argue that if any highly reactive $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{H}_2)_a$ complexes were to be formed from $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ species upon exposure of the latter to H_2 in the presence of C_2H_4 , it could be very difficult to detect such species by FTIR due to very low surface concentrations.

To better understand the FTIR data shown in Fig. 8, we have also modeled $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{H})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_a$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_a$ complexes representing intermediate structures that can potentially be formed during the exposure of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ to a $\text{H}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ mixture. In the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{H})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_a$ structure, the binding energy of ethene is -57 kJ/mol (-92 kJ/mol when dispersion correction is included, Table S1), which is the same as that in the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_a$ structure (Table 3). The ν_{NO} vibrational frequencies are expected to appear at 1793 and 1725 cm^{-1} and these values deviate by -2 and 19 cm^{-1} , respectively, from the bands observed experimentally (i.e., 1795 and 1706 cm^{-1}). These experimental ν_{NO} bands could also be attributed to the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_a$ complex with calculated ν_{NO} frequencies of 1788 and 1724 cm^{-1} that deviate by -7 and 18 cm^{-1} , respectively, from the corresponding experimental values. Thus, the formation of significant amounts of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{H})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_a$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_a$ complexes can reasonably explain the appearance of the new ν_{NO} bands at 1795 and 1706 cm^{-1} under the $\text{H}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ flow and imply that $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2_a$ complexes can activate not only C_2H_4 but also H_2 and exhibit hydrogenation

activity. Indeed, from our DFT results, one can also conclude that ethene hydrogenation to ethyl is exothermic in electronic energy by -74 kJ/mol (-72 kJ/mol, when dispersion is taken into account) when this process occurs on the single-site $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes, while the same reaction is known to be less exothermic or even endothermic in electronic energy on flat surfaces such as Pd(111) and Pt(111).^{71,72}

3.7 Catalytic properties of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY30}$. The available examples in the literature indicating that Rh nitrosyl complexes can be used as hydrogenation catalysts are limited to homogeneous liquid phase systems. Collman et al. have reported that while the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ complex does not form a stable adduct with H_2 , it can effectively catalyze cyclohexene hydrogenation in dichloromethane at room temperature and atmospheric pressure.²⁴ The same complex was also found to be active for hydrogenation of 1-hexene.^{24,26} Zou et al. have used a $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{dcpe})$ complex with bent NO and chelating diphosphine ligands in DMSO for hydrogenation of CO_2 to formic acid at 50°C and a total pressure of 3 atm with a calculated TON of 106 after 16 h.²⁷ In this case, the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{dcpe})(\text{H})_2$ intermediates was confirmed by ^1H NMR. It has also been reported that $[\text{Rh}(\text{NO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{L}]$ (where L is benzoquinone) complexes catalyze the hydrogenation of 1-hexene, cyclohexene, and styrene, as well as the selective hydrogenation of 1,3-cyclohexadiene to cyclohexene but their activity is low.²⁵

Figure 9. TOF for the formation of C₂H₆ as a function of time over a Rh(NO)₂/HY30 catalyst. (Reaction temperature 25°C; GHSV= 60,000 ml/(g·h); feed composition: 76 Torr C₂H₄/608 Torr H₂/He balance).

To the best of our knowledge, no reports related to supported rhodium nitrosyl complexes are available to date. However, it has been reported that Rh(C₂H₄)₂/HY30, Rh(CO)₂/HY30, and Rh(CO)(H)_x/HY30 materials are catalytically active for the hydrogenation of C₂H₄ to C₂H₆ at 25°C and atmospheric pressure.^{17-19,35} Since our DFT calculations suggest that the formation of Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄)_a, Rh(NO)₂(H)(C₂H₄)_a, and Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₅)_a complexes from Rh(NO)₂_a species is favorable in terms of electronic energy and, therefore, the site-isolated Rh(NO)₂_a complexes could be catalytically active, we have tested this hypothesis with the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample in a flow reactor under conditions described in the experimental section.

Figure 10. TOF for the formation of C₄ hydrocarbons as a function of time over a Rh(NO)₂/HY30 catalyst. (Reaction temperature 25°C; GHSV= 60,000 ml/(g·h); feed composition: 76 Torr C₂H₄/608 Torr H₂/He balance).

The results of the catalytic measurements are summarized in Figs. 9 and 10 and Tables 5 and 6. When the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample was exposed to a 76 Torr C₂H₄/608 Torr H₂/He mixture at 25°C, C₂H₆ immediately appeared in the effluent and the initial TOF for the formation of C₂H₆ was found to be $1.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The C₂H₄ hydrogenation activity of this sample continued to increase

Table 5. Catalytic data for the C₂H₄+H₂ reaction over Rh(NO)₂/HY30 at 25°C.

Time on stream	C ₂ H ₆ , TOFx10 ³ , s ⁻¹	C ₄ H ₁₀ , TOFx10 ³ , s ⁻¹	C ₄ H ₈ , TOFx10 ³ , s ⁻¹	C ₂ H ₆ , mol %	C ₄ H ₁₀ , mol %	1-C ₄ H ₈ , mol %	cis-C ₄ H ₈ , mol %	trans-C ₄ H ₈ , mol %
5 min	1.3	-	0.03	98	-	1.0	0.3	0.7
21 h	10.0	0.1	6.6	60	1	6	9	24

Table 6. Reaction orders for the C₂H₄+H₂ reaction over Rh(NO)₂/HY30 at 25°C.

Product	Reaction order
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	in H ₂	in C ₂ H ₄
C ₂ H ₆	0.5	0.4
Total C ₄ H ₈	0.5	1.0
n-butane	0.6	0.6
1-butene	0.3	1.2
Cis-2-butene	0.5	0.9
Trans-2-butene	0.6	0.9

with time on stream until it reached a value of $10 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ after 21 h (Fig. 9). Since changes in TOF values were not significant (i.e., less than 1%) during the last 5 h on stream, it appears that a steady state hydrogenation activity is reached at that point. However, C₂H₆ was not the only product formed over the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 material, as the formation of various C₄ hydrocarbons was also observed (Fig. 10). Results of Fig. 10 further show that 1-butene, cis-2-butene, and trans-2-butene constitute the majority of the C₄ species formed. TOF curves characterizing the formation of cis-2-butene and trans-2-butene exhibit similar patterns, as both increase during the first 7 h, reach maxima between 7 and 9 h, and slightly decline thereafter. The formation of 1-butene follows a different pattern, as it increases during the first 5 h, exhibits an inflection point between 5 and 10 h, and continues to increase thereafter. The formation rates of these three C₄ hydrocarbons appear to be related, consistent with several previous literature reports indicating that 1-butene is a primary product of C₂H₄ oligomerization, while its subsequent isomerization leads to cis-2-butene and trans-2-butene species.⁷³⁻⁷⁵ Finally, the formation of small amounts of n-butane and trace amounts of 1,3-butadiene were also detected in the reactor effluent.

Table 5 provides a summary of catalytic data for the initial period of time (i.e., 5 min) and after 21 h on stream. From these data, it is evident that the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample exhibits primarily C₂H₄ hydrogenation activity during the initial period of time, producing C₂H₆ with a 98 mol % selectivity. After 21 h on stream, the overall activity increases by a factor of 10, but the selectivity to C₂H₆ drops to 60 mol %. This is due to the simultaneous increase of C₂H₄ oligomerization activity with a combined TOF of $6.7 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and an overall C₄ selectivity of 40 mol %.

When the activity of this sample reached steady state, two additional sets of measurements were performed to determine reaction orders with respect to the reactants. In the first set, the partial pressure of C₂H₄ was kept constant at 76 Torr, while the partial pressure of H₂ varied in the 76-608 Torr range. In the second set, the partial pressure of H₂ was kept constant at 380 Torr,

while the partial pressure of C₂H₄ varied in the 76-304 Torr range. The H₂ and C₂H₄ reaction orders determined from these measurements are shown in Table 6 for each product formed. For C₂H₄ hydrogenation to C₂H₆, the reaction orders in H₂ and C₂H₄ were found to be 0.5 and 0.4, respectively. This result indicates competitive adsorption of H₂ and C₂H₄ on the active sites (i.e., supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes) and strongly suggests that both of these reactants participate in rate limiting steps. Flat Rh surfaces, supported Rh particles with sizes in the 1-100 nm range, and small Rh clusters supported on different supports including zeolites are known to be much more active for C₂H₄ hydrogenation than the HY zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes examined herein.^{50,76,77} However, all these materials typically exhibit first and zero order dependences on H₂ and C₂H₄, respectively.^{50,76,77} These literature examples indicate that regardless of their size, the surface of Rh particles or clusters is nearly saturated with C₂H₄ under hydrogenation conditions. Molecular [RhCl(C₂H₄)(PiPr₃)₂]₂ dimers incorporating C₂H₄ ligands represent the smallest assembly of Rh atoms previously examined and they were also found to be active for hydrogenation of C₂H₄ to C₂H₆ in a toluene solution with the reaction also being first order in hydrogen and zero order in C₂H₄.⁷⁸ In contrast to all these examples, the data of Table 6 demonstrate that the hydrogenation of C₂H₄ follows different kinetics over Rh(NO)₂/HY30, consistent with the absence of Rh aggregates, clusters, and dimers on the surface of this material.

The data of Table 6 further show that the formation of C₄ hydrocarbons depends more strongly on the ethene partial pressure and roughly follows first order kinetics. This result is not surprising since two C₂H₄ molecules are required to form C₄ species as compared to one needed to form C₂H₆. The results shown in Table 6 are also consistent with literature reports indicating a first-order dependence on the alkene partial pressure in the dimerization and polymerization of C₂H₄ over molecular and supported metal complexes.^{73,74,79-81} While the mechanism of C₂H₄ oligomerization over molecular metal complexes is not completely established, it is generally assumed that the reaction follows the typical Cossee-Arlman scheme with M-H species acting as the active intermediates in a catalytic cycle that includes the alkyl migration in C_nH_{2n}-M-C_nH_{2n+1} complexes to form M-C_{2n}H_{4n+1} metal-alkyl intermediates from which the oligomer is released via the beta-hydride elimination.^{14,82}

It is not clear at the moment how C₄ hydrocarbons are formed over the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 material. Since it has been shown that molecular [Rh(C₂H₄)₂Cl]₂ complexes are active for

dimerization of C_2H_4 into C_4H_8 species,^{14,82} one can envision that zeolite-supported $Rh(NO)_2$ complexes could also exhibit the same type of chemistry. To explore this possibility, $Rh(NO)_2$ _a complexes incorporating cis-2-butene, trans-2-butene, and 1-butene ligands were modeled and the results are shown in Tables 3 and 4, and S1 in SI. The $Rh(NO)_2(\text{cis-}C_4H_8)$ _a complex appears to be the most stable, while complexes $Rh(NO)_2(\text{trans-}C_4H_8)$ _a and $Rh(NO)_2(1-C_4H_8)$ _a are less stable by 10 and 11 kJ/mol than it, respectively. The binding energy (in terms of electronic energy) of cis-2-butene, trans-2-butene, and 1-butene ligands to the $Rh(NO)_2$ _a complex are -63, -53 and -52 kJ/mol (-120, -116, and -110 kJ/mol when dispersion correction is taken into account, Table S1 in SI), respectively, suggesting that $Rh(NO)_2(C_4H_8)$ species could exist under reaction conditions. Furthermore, the ν_{NO} bands of such complexes at 1802-1817 and 1731-1745 cm^{-1} reasonably agree with the ν_{NO} bands observed at 1810 and 1716 cm^{-1} upon exposure of $Rh(NO)_2/HY30$ to C_2H_4 (Fig. 4). Finally, our calculations show that dimerization of two ethene molecules to butene is exothermic in electronic energy by -126 to -148 kJ/mol.

We considered also a complex that may be an intermediate for ethene dimerization - with $CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2$ fragment forming five membered ring with Rh center, $Rh(NO)_2(CH_2)_4$ _5R_a. This complex is by 40 kJ/mol (28 kJ/mol when dispersion interactions are taken into account) more stable than the dinitrosyl complex with two coordinated ethene molecules but it is by 102 kJ/mol (108 kJ/mol with dispersion) less stable than the dinitrosyl complex with coordinated cis-butene. Thus, indeed from the point of view of the electronic energies, the cyclic complex may be considered as potential intermediate for butene formation. It may also rationalize why only ethene dimerization but not polymerization can occur on $Rh(NO)_2$ species in the zeolites. The calculated set of ν_{NO} values of the $Rh(NO)_2(CH_2)_4$ _5R_a complex do not fit to the experimentally observed pairs of bands obtained upon exposure of $Rh(NO)_2/HY30$ to C_2H_4 . This may be connected to the short lifetime of the intermediated species, if they are formed.

The most intriguing result in Table 6 is the dependence of C_2H_4 oligomerization on the H_2 partial pressure (Table 6). For the overall C_4H_8 formation process, the reaction order in H_2 was found to be 0.5, while the corresponding reaction orders in H_2 for 1-butene, cis-2-butene, and trans-2-butene were found to be 0.3, 0.5, and 0.6, respectively. Since neither C_2H_4 dimerization nor C_4H_8 isomerization require H_2 to proceed, this result appears to be counter-intuitive at first glance and only limited literature reports are available to shed some additional light on this issue.

It is known for example, that H₂ can be used during the polymerization of C₂H₄ over supported catalysts as a chain-transfer agent to control the molecular weight of the polyethylene formed. Typically, the C₂H₄ polymerization activity of Ziegler-Natta catalysts declines in the presence of H₂.⁸³⁻⁸⁵ However, other reports show that the process outcome depends on the concentration of H₂. For example, Mikenas et al.⁸¹ have shown a promotional effect of H₂ on the C₂H₄ polymerization activity of a LFeCl₂/MgCl₂ catalyst when the H₂ concentration is in the 9-17% range. This effect was explained on the basis of H₂ activation on polymerization sites that are partially blocked by strongly bound unsaturated oligomers and therefore, become inactive. The activation of H₂ leads to the formation of M–H hydride species and alkenes that can to continue the polymerization process on such sites.

Along these lines, the dependence of C₂H₄ hydrogenation and dimerization over Rh(NO)₂/HY30 on H₂ implies that hydrogen is activated on the active Rh sites under reaction conditions and the activated hydrogen species are involved in rate-limiting steps for both reactions. Since our DFT calculations show that the formation of Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄) complexes is energetically favorable, it is possible that the activation of H₂ by these species could yield Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₅) complexes. In fact, the such complexes could be important intermediates for both the hydrogenation and oligomerization pathways, as their further interaction with hydrogen yields C₂H₆, while C₂H₄ insertion into (NO)₂Rh–C₂H₅ bonds can form a Rh(NO)₂(σ-C₄H₉) complex, which through subsequent β-hydrogen elimination can yield C₄H₈ and Rh(NO)₂(H). This type of chemistry is well known for a variety of organometallic complexes of different metals in solution, including those of Rh.⁸⁶ Therefore, it is possible that the zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ species resemble the properties of molecular complexes to some extent. However, in the case of the zeolite-supported complexes, the formation of Rh(NO)₂(H) is energetically unfavorable based on our calculations, suggesting that these unstable species are immediately converted into Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₅) in the presence of gas-phase C₂H₄.

Additional experiments performed with a C₂H₄/D₂ feed reinforce our conclusions and provide evidence that the Rh sites participate, at least in part, in the formation of the C₄ species. In these measurements, the Rh(NO)₂/HY30 sample was exposed to a C₂H₄/H₂ feed for 21 h to stabilize its performance and then the H₂ in the feed was replaced by D₂ at the same partial pressure. The results obtained show K_H/K_D values of 0.7 and 0.9 for the formation of C₂H₆ and C₄ hydrocarbons,

respectively. These values indicate an inverse kinetic isotope effect in the hydrogenation and oligomerization of C_2H_4 over this material. Literature reports indicate that the majority of R–H vs R–D reductive elimination reactions over organometallic complexes in solution are characterized by such an inverse kinetic isotope effect due to the increased thermodynamic stability of the M–D vs M–H agostic intermediates, thus effectively lowering the transition state energy and leading to higher reaction rates.^{82,87} Therefore, the inverse kinetic isotope effect observed in our case suggests the involvement of reductive elimination steps with agostic intermediates formed on the Rh sites for both the ethylene hydrogenation and oligomerization pathways, although the effect is more pronounced in the case of hydrogenation.

This result, however, does not eliminate the potential role of the support in both reaction pathways. In fact, previous literature reports have shown that the support can either assist in the formation of reaction intermediates and products or actively participate in catalysis.^{15,69,88,89} In the latter case, for example, the acidic protons of the zeolite can initiate and carry the sequence of C_2H_4 oligomerization steps without participation of the Rh sites. In such a case, however, one expects that hydrogen activated on Rh sites and migrating to the support facilitates at least some steps of the C_2H_4 oligomerization pathway. At the moment, our experimental results do not provide any direct evidence in support of such a scheme. However, it is possible that the dependence of the rate of oligomerization on the hydrogen partial pressure can be rationalized even if the role of hydrogen activated on Rh sites is simply limited to the facilitation of the desorption of C_4 hydrocarbons formed on the support.

Finally, while the catalytic results presented herein clearly demonstrate the remarkable ability of site-isolated $Rh(NO)_2$ complexes supported on the HY30 zeolite to activate C_2H_4 and H_2 and, therefore, catalyze hydrogenation and oligomerization of C_2H_4 under ambient conditions, these results are not sufficient to provide a clear distinction between the role of the $Rh(NO)_2$ complexes and the zeolite support in these two reactions. Additional efforts are required to further clarify these issues.

3.8 Imaging of $Rh(NO)_2/HY30$ used for C_2H_4 hydrogenation. It has been shown previously that the selectivity of HY zeolite-supported $Rh(C_2H_4)_2$ complexes for dimerization vs. hydrogenation of C_2H_4 can be tuned by regulation of the feed composition, which controls the ratio

of mononuclear rhodium complexes to clusters, with the latter being active in the hydrogenation pathway.³⁵ Therefore, one need to address the potential formation of Rh clusters from the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2$ complexes under the reaction conditions used in our experiments. To dismiss unambiguously any such doubt, high-resolution STEM images of the $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}30$ sample used in catalysis for 21 h have been recorded. Figs. 11 and 12 show representative Z-contrast HAADF HRSTEM images of the spent $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}30$ material. The image shown in Fig. 11 has a relatively low magnification to overview a large area of the sample. At this resolution, the zeolite channels are clearly observed but no Rh nanoparticles and/or clusters can be identified.

Figure 11. HAADF Z-contrast HRSTEM image of a $\text{Rh}(\text{NO})_2/\text{HY}30$ catalyst that was used for ethene hydrogenation at 25°C for 21 h.

Figure 12. HAADF Z-contrast HRSTEM image of a Rh(NO)₂/HY30 catalyst that was used for ethene hydrogenation at 25°C for 21 h.

The image shown in Fig. 12 has higher resolution at which supercage openings are clearly observed in the zeolite [110] projection as black spots. In this case, individual Rh atoms can also be identified as bright spots in some areas of this Z-contrast image (circled in green for clarity), while no indication of any Rh agglomeration is observed. Overall, these STEM images unambiguously prove that Rh does not aggregate under reaction conditions and retains its single-site dispersion even after 21 h of catalysis.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Rh(CO)₂ complexes supported on various dealuminated HY zeolites were used as precursors for the surface-mediated synthesis of Rh(NO)₂ species. The carbonyl ligands of the former react with gas phase NO to form Rh(NO)₂ complexes. This process takes place on all HY zeolites examined regardless of their Si/Al ratio. The Rh(NO)₂ complexes thus formed are 14-electron species with NO ligands significantly deviating from a linear configuration and are characterized by a set of well-defined ν_{NO} bands (i.e., 1855 and 1779 cm⁻¹) in their FTIR spectra. DFT calculations provide strong evidence that three different pairs of oxygen atoms in the zeolite framework can anchor these species on the zeolite support. Rh(NO)₂ complexes attached differently to the zeolite framework apparently coexist on the zeolite surface and it is not possible to identify experimentally each type of these species due to the broad nature and overlap of their characteristic ν_{NO} bands.

The principle difference between zeolite-supported 14-electron Rh(NO)₂ and 16-electron Rh(CO)₂ complexes is the presence of an empty d-orbital at the rhodium center in the Rh(NO)₂ complex that allows for coordination of a third electron-donating ligand to the complex. Therefore, zeolite-supported Rh(NO)₂ species can react with C₂H₄ at room temperature without substitution of nitrosyl ligands to form 16-electron Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₄) complexes that incorporate only weakly bound C₂H₄ and exist only when C₂H₄ is present in the gas phase. While no reaction was observed during direct exposure of Rh(NO)₂ to H₂ at room temperature, the simultaneous presence of C₂H₄ and H₂ in the gas phase results in the formation of Rh(NO)₂(C₂H₅) and/or Rh(NO)₂(H)(C₂H₄)

complexes, as indicated by the results of FTIR measurements and DFT calculations. The ability of Rh(NO)₂/HY to catalyze ethene hydrogenation and dimerization at room temperature further confirms the H₂ activation by this material. Initially, the Rh(NO)₂/HY sample exhibits primarily C₂H₄ hydrogenation activity with a TOF of 1.3·10⁻³ s⁻¹. The hydrogenation activity of this sample increases with time on stream until a value of 0.01 s⁻¹ is reached after 21 h. However, at that point the Rh(NO)₂/HY sample also shows a substantial C₂H₄ oligomerization activity with a combined TOF of 6.7·10⁻³ s⁻¹. Both hydrogenation and dimerization pathways depend on the partial pressures of ethylene and hydrogen. While the dependence on H₂ is nearly the same for both reactions (i.e., ~0.5), the dependence on the ethylene partial pressure differs by a factor of 2. An inverse kinetic isotope effect was observed, suggesting the involvement of reductive elimination steps with agostic intermediates formed on the Rh sites during both ethylene hydrogenation and oligomerization pathways. Such behavior parallels the catalytic behavior of molecular Rh complexes in solution. HRSTEM images of the spent material unambiguously prove that Rh does not aggregate under the reaction conditions used and retains its single-site dispersion even after 21 h of catalysis. Overall, this work shows that the ligand environment of supported Rh complexes significantly affects the surface chemistry observed and represents the first example demonstrating that zeolite-anchored Rh nitrosyl complexes are catalyzing hydrocarbon hydrogenation and dimerization reactions.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Supplementary figures, including EXAFS fittings, mass spectra, electronic configurations of faujasites-supported Rh(NO)₂ complexes, and FTIR. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

OSA acknowledges the University of South Carolina for its partial financial support of this work (ASPIRE grant 15510-16-41851). HAA and GNV are grateful for the support by the Horizon2020 program of the European Commission (project Materials Networking - grant agreement 692146, and COST Action MP1306). HAA acknowledges partial financial support by the Bulgarian Science Fund (project DFNI-T02/20).

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